

Influencing factors of soil organic carbon in mainland Portugal: Geospatial, Socioeconomic, and Machine Learning Approaches

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Abstract

Purpose | The effective management of soil quality is crucial in the context of intense market and supply chain competition. This article aims to highlight the importance of the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) from the FAO Soils Portal for analysing soil characteristics in Portugal. By integrating new variables related to climate conditions and socioeconomic dynamics, the article seeks to enhance the understanding of the interconnections between soil attributes and other indicators.

Methodology/Approach | The article utilized the HWSD v2.0, expanded with additional datasets including the Land Use and Occupation Map (COS2007v3.0), CHELSA climate data, and socioeconomic data from the National Institute of Statistics (INE). Various machine learning models, including Random Forest, XGB, Neural Networks, and Support Vector Regression, are employed to analyse both categorical and numerical data. The models are evaluated using cross-validation and performance metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and R-squared (R^2).

Expected Results | The results demonstrate the potential of the chosen datasets for interpreting soil dynamics and interconnections within the Portuguese context. Key predictors such as total nitrogen, impermeable layer, soil drainage and carbon-to-nitrogen ratio are identified as critical factors influencing soil properties. The integration of diverse datasets provided a holistic view of soil characteristics, revealing distinct regions with similar soil properties through clustering analysis.

Conclusion | The findings underscore the effectiveness of machine learning models in soil analysis, with Random Forest and XGB showing high accuracy. The article's insights can inform targeted soil management practices and policymaking, enhancing soil health and carbon sequestration efforts. Future research should expand the dataset to include more diverse regions and explore advanced machine learning techniques for even more detailed soil analysis.

Keywords | Soil Organic Carbon, Geospatial Analysis, Sustainable Land management, Machine learning, Soil Modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

The soil has been neglected for some years, but in recent decades, its role as a carbon sink has gained significant attention due to the growing urgency of addressing climate change and global warming. For instance, soils contain approximately three times more carbon than the atmosphere and vegetation combined (Lal, 2004), highlighting their critical role in mitigating climate change.

In response, several countries and international bodies have implemented directives aimed at enhancing soil carbon sequestration. The European Union's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) encourages practices such as minimal to no-till farming, which reduce soil disturbance and enhance carbon storage (Smith et al., 2014).

The European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy are central to the EU's approach to reducing its carbon footprint and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The European Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, with agriculture playing a significant role in achieving these goals through carbon sequestration and sustainable land management (European Commission, 2021). The Farm to Fork Strategy, introduced in 2020, complements this by focusing on reducing the environmental impact of the food system, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting organic farming, and improving soil health. By incentivizing sustainable practices in farming, these initiatives seek to enhance soil carbon storage while simultaneously mitigating the effects of climate change.

These regulations aim to balance greenhouse gases by improving sequestration, reducing emissions, or both, ultimately working to reduce human society's carbon footprint. As such, this work arches over the factor influencing the soil organic carbon (SOC) as pivotal factor in new policies. To better understand the influence of various other characteristics on SOC, several databases are used to explore possible relations between variables.

2. METHODS

2.1 Description of datasets

The first step in this article is the selection of relevant databases which would allow for a better understanding of the influences governing soil properties, which could be linked to the organic carbon content in the soil.

2.1.1 Harmonized World Soil Database version 2.0

The first database used is the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD v2.0), being developed by FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) and IIASA (International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis), particularly adapted for biophysical models and agroecological queries (FAO & IIASA, 2023a). This database consolidates information from several sources, including the European Soil Database, the 1:1 million soil map of China, and several national soil maps from Afghanistan, Ghana, and Türkiye. The database possesses a spatial resolution of around 1 km (30 arc seconds by 30 arc seconds), rendering it appropriate for global, continental, and regional modelling. The database is a joint initiative comprising organisations such as ISRIC, ESNB, and CAS. It is revised in 2013 (HWSD v1.2) and 2023 (HWSD v2.0). HWSD v2.0 enhanced prior iterations by incorporating data from national soil databases, providing comprehensive soil attributes for seven distinct soil layers, and implementing a uniform soil reference system that integrates FAO1990 standards with the World Reference Base for Soil Resources. A modified edition (v2.01) is issued in September 2023.

The HWSD v2.0 includes detailed information on soil mapping units, general soil unit information, and specific physical and chemical soil unit characteristics across seven depth layers. The database fields cover a wide range of attributes, such as soil texture, bulk density, organic carbon content, pH, and cation exchange capacity. The harmonization process ensures that data from different sources is standardized and integrated, providing a consistent and reliable dataset for various applications.

The data on soil mapping units are obtained from various sources, including ESDB, SOTWIS, DSMW, and national soil maps from China, Afghanistan, Ghana, and

Turkey. The soil mapping units are categorised into the classifications SMU, WRB 2022, and FAO90.

Soil attributes are provided for each depth layer (D1 to D7) separately. For reference the upper and lower limits of the soil layers concerned can be seen in Table I.

Table I - Depth of top and bottom layers in HWSDv2.0 Database.

<i>Depth layer</i>	<i>Depth of the Top layer (in centimeters)</i>	<i>Depth of the bottom layer (in centimeters)</i>
D1	0	20
D2	20	40
D3	40	60
D4	60	80
D5	80	100
D6	100	150
D7	150	200

Each soil mapping unit provides general information on soil units, including the dominant soil unit and up to eleven associated soils. The sequence within the mapping unit is presented in order of percentage share, with the dominant soil having sequence one. The share of each soil unit within the mapping unit is presented as a percentage, summing up to 100%. The internal database identifier is used to identify the national or local soil classification system. Since the dataset contains a large variety of soil unit symbols, these will not be extensively listed here, however they are freely available in the Technical Report, particularly section 2.3.3 Soil Attributes per depth layer (FAO & IIASA, 2023a, 2023b).

Database limitations disclaimer

Despite its extensive coverage and detailed information, the HWSD v2.0 has some limitations. It combines soil inventories gathered at different times, scales, and precision, which may affect its reliability for national studies. Therefore, it is recommended to use national-level harmonized soil databases for more accurate results in specific regions. The European Soil Database is an essential resource, yet its accuracy and precision have not been quantified. The Scientific Committee of the

ESDB aims to address this issue by distributing data and soliciting user feedback as part of the validation process. The responsibility for the accuracy of spatial and attribute data lies with the contributing organisations. The soil polygons on the printed European Soil Map are digitized in the late 1980s and have been elaborated, checked, and modified by national experts under the 1:1M soil geographical database project. While some areas have been partially corrected, systematic checks on the content and integrity of the polygons have not been made. These polygons represent the best representation of soils of Europa at the scale of 1:1,000,000, but they must be accepted as such. Soil data in member states' national archives is aggregated based on soil units or classes belonging to national soil classifications, which differ significantly from the FAO system used for the EU Soil Map. National data used to compile the original map in 1972-78 had to be re-interpreted to fit a different classification system, which worked more effectively in some countries than in others.

Attribute coding is similar to soil map unit polygons, but the accuracy and integrity of these data remain the responsibility of the national experts who supplied them. Technical consistency checks have not been made, and data are accepted 'as supplied' (European Commission, n.d.; Panagos et al., 2012, 2022).

For Portugal's mainland, the data which is presented in the HWSD v2.0 dataset is sourced from the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC). This information contains various metrics of chemical and physical soil properties, with some extrapolation for data completion.

In fact the data is so complete, that out of the 2882 Portuguese parishes, only 22 are left out, representing 0.76% percent of the total number of parishes. As such, the HWSD v2.0 is the first selected database to integrate the article, due to its richness of information about Portuguese mainland (Panagos et al., 2022).

2.1.2 Land Use and Occupation Map

The second dataset selected is the Land Use and Occupation Map (**COS2007v3.0**), from Directorate-General for Territory (DGT). The dataset is a detailed thematic map of land use and occupation for mainland Portugal, developed by the DGT as part of

the Land Occupation Monitoring System. The COS2007v3.0 map, produced using high-resolution orthorectified aerial images and auxiliary databases, provides comprehensive information on land use and occupation with a minimum mapping unit of 1 hectare and a scale of 1:25,000 (Direção-Geral do Território, 2022).

The COS2007v3.0 includes 83 classes of land use and occupation, organized hierarchically, and is part of a consistent series that includes maps for 1995, 2010, 2015, and 2018. This series ensures spatial and temporal consistency in land use data.

To ensure the accuracy and compatibility of both HWSDv2.0 and Land Use data, a shorter time gap between data sources is sought, as soil and its occupation evolves over time. The data from HWSDv2.0 is compiled from samples taken in various periods, the most recent in the year 2004. In knowing so, we aimed to provide results as close to land use and occupation of the data, as possible, which translates into the main reason behind selecting a Land Use and Occupation Map of closer date to 2004, even though newer versions exist.

2.1.3 Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas

The third dataset is used containing bioclimatic indexes for precipitation and average temperature from CHELSA (Karger et al., 2017, 2020). The CHELSA (Climatologies at High Resolution for the Earth's Land Surface Areas) database is a high-resolution global climate dataset maintained by the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow, and Landscape Research (WSL). It offers climate data at a precision of 30 arc seconds (about 1 km), rendering it one of the most comprehensive climate data sets accessible. CHELSA encompasses climate layers for multiple temporal intervals and variables, ranging from the Last Glacial Maximum to the present, as well as several prospective scenarios.

This article utilised precipitation (PR) and mean annual temperature (TAS) data from this source throughout numerous years. The dataset encompasses yearly mean values, standard deviations, and coefficients of variation for precipitation and temperature, covering the period from 1991 to 2021. These metrics offer an extensive summary of climatic changes over the last thirty years, facilitating a thorough examination of variability and enduring patterns. The article seeks to

evaluate variations in precipitation and temperature by integrating these climate indicators, which are essential for comprehending wider environmental and agricultural consequences.

2.1.4 National Institute of Statistics

The fourth dataset is retrieved from INE (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2003). This data consisted of several independent datasets. The first dataset contains the information pertaining the managers/directors of agricultural enterprises, particularly, gender and age of managers/directors of agricultural explorations, from 1989 to 2019, with a focus on the age groups of 16-24 years, 25-34 years, 45-54 years, 55-64 years, 65+ years, for men and women. The survey had information for all Portuguese parishes.

The next dataset used in this article focuses on the agricultural sector, categorized into Geographical Localization (NUTS - 2013), Economic Dimensions (euros), and Technical-Economic Orientation. The classifications of economic dimensions include MP (Very Small) for values below 8,000 euros, P (Small) for 8,000 to 25,000 euros, M (Medium) for 25,000 to 100,000 euros, and G (Large) for values exceeding 100,000 euros. The Technical-Economic Orientation includes specialized explorations for vegetable production, arable crops, intensive farming and floriculture, permanent crops, and animal production, as well as mixed farming systems. The article also covers specialized explorations in polyculture, mixed crop and livestock farming, and non-classified explorations. Additionally, the dataset includes details on specialized explorations for vegetable production, arable crops, intensive farming and floriculture, permanent crops, animal production, and mixed farming, as well as non-classified explorations.

Another dataset utilized in this article focuses on agricultural machinery, providing a comprehensive overview of equipment distribution across different geographical locations (NUTS - 2013) over multiple decades. The dataset includes information on the total number of agricultural machines, as well as specific categories such as wheeled and tracked tractors, motor cultivators, power hoes, motor mowers, and

combine harvesters. Data is available in decennial intervals, covering the years 1989, 1999, 2009, 2019. Each time frame details the number of agricultural machines by category and region, offering insights into the evolution of mechanization in the agricultural sector. By analysing these historical trends, it is possible to assess changes in agricultural machinery adoption, technological advancements, and regional disparities in equipment availability. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for understanding the progression of mechanization and its impact on agricultural productivity over time.

The next selected dataset focuses on irrigated land and examines the distribution of farms with access to irrigation (%) based on geographical location (NUTS - 2013). This dataset includes decennial data from 2019 and 2009, covering various categories of irrigation availability. Specifically, it provides insights into the total distribution of farms with irrigation access, as well as a breakdown by type of irrigation system: state collective, private collective, and individual irrigation. This dataset allows for an analysis of trends in irrigation accessibility over time, highlighting shifts in the prevalence and management of irrigation systems within different geographical regions.

Another dataset selected for this article focuses on burned land data, spanning multiple decades and capturing key wildfire-related metrics. It includes information on the number of fires, the burned area in hectares (Ha), the total area of each administrative region (Parish) in hectares, and the percentage of the area affected by fires. This data is systematically recorded from 1975 to 2023, providing a comprehensive overview of fire occurrences and their impact over time. This dataset enables a detailed analysis of fire trends, regional susceptibility, and the extent of land affected. Such data is crucial for understanding long-term patterns, assessing the effectiveness of fire prevention measures, and informing future land management and policy decisions.

The final dataset utilized from this source pertains to population density, measured in inhabitants per square kilometre, based on the place of residence recorded in the

Census. This dataset includes data from the 2021 Census (NUTS - 2013) as well as the 2011 Census (NUTS - 2013), providing a decennial comparison of total population density across different geographical regions.

2.2 Data integration

The data used here, as mentioned above, came from a variety of sources. While in most cases the data is labelled in a very straightforward format, that is not always the case for every database. As such for example, in the case of the data collected from the National Institute of Statistics (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2003).

The databases are used in conjunction to extract and transform the data into a file format that is easier to work with, in this case .xlsx format. In order to begin processing the data, some review of similar works is needed. The article by Awais et al. (2023), stresses the significance of employing artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) platforms for comprehensive, precise, and rapid soil research, especially within the framework of sustainable farming practices. The authors emphasise the benefits of AI data processing compared to traditional statistical methods, especially in managing extensive geospatial non-numeric data and producing noise-free outcomes.

Additionally, Wadoux et al. (2019) presents a deep learning model for digital soil mapping (DSM) that amalgamates multi-source data to enhance the precision of soil property predictions.

Our research similarly utilises these advantages by integrating multiple datasets, including climatic data from CHELSA and socioeconomic data from INE, to offer a thorough understanding of soil features. The application of machine learning algorithms in our research not only improves the precision of soil property forecasts but also facilitates the advancement of sustainable land management methods.

To start exploring the databases some operations are needed to warrant the data is within a single, intercomparable referential. The HWSv2.0 had a lot of information; however, it needed to be georeferenced in order to be used. For this purpose the data, particularly the raster file, is georeferenced using QGIS (QGIS Development 8

Team, 2024). This allowed to add information about Portuguese districts, municipalities and parishes.

When calculating averages, it is often necessary to handle missing values to ensure the accuracy of the results. In this article, missing values are managed by normalizing the weights of each valid value. This approach ensures that the remaining data points are accurately represented, even when some values are missing (Nugroho et al., 2021). The process involved identifying valid values, disregarding negative ones, adjust weight sum, and re-normalize weights. Disregarded negative values change total weights, while remaining weights must be adjusted to equal 1. Re-normalization involves re-normalizing weights for remaining values to equal 1.

The application of normalization in soil data, is done to produce an intermediate dataset. The results per parish are achieved by averaging the number of each soil type inside each parish (parish), considering the equidistant data points. These values are then further processed to calculate the average for each municipality (municipality), using the area of each parish as the weight value for the municipality. This approach ensures the most accurate results possible for each municipality.

After handling the data, the process of creating, training, and testing various machine learning models began. This process is based on a review of various algorithms and is developed using Python (v3.12.3) with the Spyder (v6.0) IDE. The algorithms used included:

- Random Forest (RF)
- Extreme Gradient Boost (XGB)
- Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
- Support Vector Regression (SVR)
- Elastic Net Regression (ENR)

The data is divided into two parts: categorical data and numerical data, creating two datasets for each parish. These datasets are then used to train and test the models. The performance of these models is evaluated, and the most important features

(predictors) are identified for each model. For more details, please refer to the Results in section 3.

2.3 Model Building

Machine learning is a subset of Artificial Intelligence that aims to mimic human cognitive functions in learning and problem-solving processes. The goal of machine learning is to identify the model and its optimal parameters that achieve the highest unbiased predictive accuracy for a given problem and related dataset. For the wide variety and large quantity of data at hand, several algorithms are selected for testing. Random forests are a statistical learning method developed by Leo Breiman in 2001, known for their excellent predictive performance and flexibility. They are suitable for both supervised classification and regression problems, handling both qualitative and quantitative explanatory variables without preprocessing. Random forests are effective with standard data and high-dimensional cases with large variables. They involve constructing multiple decision trees during training and aggregating their predictions, each built using a random subset of the training data and features. This reduces overfitting and improves generalization. The predictions of individual trees are combined to produce a final prediction that is more accurate and robust. Random forests also provide measures of variable importance, enabling the model to focus on the most relevant variables and improve interpretability. They are particularly effective in handling large datasets with high dimensionality and are less sensitive to noise compared to other algorithms like Adaboost (Breiman, 2001; Genuer & Poggi, 2020).

Extreme Gradient boosting is a scalable machine learning system for tree boosting that is widely used by data scientists to achieve state-of-the-art results in various machine learning challenges. It introduces a novel sparsity-aware algorithm for handling sparse data and a weighted quantile sketch for approximate tree learning. XGB is designed to be highly efficient, leveraging cache access patterns, data compression, and sharding to scale beyond billions of examples using fewer resources than existing systems. Its scalability and performance make it a popular choice in both academic research and industry applications (Chen & Guestrin, 2016).

Neural networks, inspired by the architecture and dynamics of the mammalian brain, consist of interconnected neurons that process data through complex networks. These networks adapt over time by forming new connections, enhancing their data-processing capabilities. In machine learning, artificial neural networks use simplified neuron models to perform various tasks, such as recognizing patterns in data and generalizing learned information to new datasets. They excel in supervised learning tasks like image recognition and machine translation, as well as unsupervised learning tasks that involve organizing large, high-dimensional datasets to detect patterns and clusters. Reinforcement learning, another application, enables agents to optimize their behaviour based on rewards and penalties. The foundational work by McCulloch and Pitts in 1943 laid the groundwork for neural network algorithms, introducing the binary threshold unit model, which remains a core component of modern neural networks (Mehlig, 2021). ANN is a proficient computing system that derives from a series of machine learning techniques that mimic the human biological neural network functioning process. It is often applied to solve complex nonlinear relationships between input and output variables. ANN uses a series of neurons to learn how certain patterns of pre-existing factors tend to produce outcomes. The multilayer perceptron (MLP) with a back-propagation type is one of the most popular ANN architectures. Deep learning is a technique that enhances ANNs by extracting nonlinear input functions from linear models, enabling the development of more complex input functions. It aims to learn feature levels of rising abstraction with minimal human intervention. Deep neural networks are trained one layer at a time using techniques like autoencoders and can be supervised or unsupervised for large datasets. They are powerful and efficient, based on distributed representational learning, and offer benefits like automatic feature selection and supervised learning operations. They can conduct automatic feature extraction, classification, and anomaly detection. Deep neural networks are best trained with GPU-based architectures, which take less time than classical CPUs (Subasi, 2020).

Support Vector Machines (SVM) are first introduced by Boser et al. (1992), and is commonly used in handwriting recognition functions and facial analysis. It is based

on linear combinations of factors and revolves around the analyses of a theoretical hyperplane learned from training data by using optimization procedures that maximize prediction. In SVM, nonlinear kernel functions are applied to convert complex nonlinear relationships into high-dimensional feature spaces. Parallel hyperplanes are generated to maximize the separation of targeted output classifications in the training data (Smola & Schölkopf, 2004).

Elastic net regression is a regularization and variable selection method that combines the properties of both ridge regression and lasso regression. Proposed by Hui Zou and Trevor Hastie, the ENR addresses some limitations of the lasso, particularly in scenarios where the number of predictors (p) is much larger than the number of observations (n). The method encourages a grouping effect, where strongly correlated predictors tend to be included or excluded from the model together, enhancing the model's interpretability and stability. This is achieved by combining the lasso's ability to produce sparse models with ridge regression's ability to handle multicollinearity among predictors. The elastic net is particularly useful for high-dimensional data and has been shown to outperform the lasso in various real-world applications and simulation studies (Zou & Hastie, 2005).

2.3.1 Testing and evaluating – cross-validation

The article employs k-fold cross-validation to randomly split data into k subsets for training and testing. This method aims to avoid heterogeneous subsets of data that could produce biased results. To address this, ten rounds of cross-validations are employed on the entire dataset. Each round involves training the model in all-but-one folds and testing it on the excluded fold. The average of the result measures from all ten rounds is then compiled for final analyses. This approach reduces bias compared to regular cross-validation. The overall accuracy from the cross-validation procedure is calculated using the average of each individual k accuracy measure. The methodology follows an outline proposed by several modern machine learning studies (Lima & Delen, 2020).

2.3.2 Performance metrics

Performance evaluation is done using commonly accepted metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), R-squared (R^2), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Explained Variance Score (EVS), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). These criteria are studied for every model, this allows for a thorough comparison.

3. RESULTS

The ML algorithms used are divided into two groups based on the type of data being handled as to maximize model accuracy.

3.1 Models used for categorical data

For the Categorical data, the models used are Random Forest, XGB and ENR. The sections herein exhibit the results of model performance for these algorithms.

3.1.1 Categorical Model Performance

The analysis of the performance of categorical models is essential for understanding the effectiveness of each approach in predicting SOC target variables using categorical variables. The models' performance is compared by model and by metric.

The Random Forest model demonstrated solid performance, the MSE is 0.0765, while the RMSE is 0.1557. The MAE is 0.0225, indicating high accuracy in predictions and the R^2 is 0.9701, showing that the model explains most of the data variability. Additionally, the EVS is 0.9701, reinforcing the model's high capacity to capture data variability.

The XGB model exhibited excellent performance with MSE score of 0.0851 and RMSE score of 0.1535. The MAE is 0.0220 and the R^2 is 0.9667, showing that the model is highly effective in explaining data variability. The EVS is 0.9668, reinforcing the robustness of the XGB model for accurate predictions.

The ENR model showed inferior performance compared to the other categorical models. The MSE is 1.0919, the RMSE is 0.6914, and the MAE is 0.3337. The R^2 is 0.2827, indicating that the model explains only a limited part of the data variability. The EVS is 0.2847, suggesting that the model may not be the best choice for accurate predictions of categorical variables.

3.1.2 Residuals of Categorical Data

Residuals represent the difference between observed values and those predicted by the model. The analysis of residuals is a crucial step in evaluating the accuracy and robustness of predictive models. The graphical representation of the residuals data can be found in ANNEX I – Residuals of numerical algorithms used. We also regarded model residuals by depth, in order to explore how each model's predictions behaviour is influenced by depth.

The XGB model predicts unbiased predictions for most sequences, with mean residuals close to zero. However, for some target variables, like Seq_5_D7, there are higher mean residuals, suggesting slight underestimation. The coefficient of variation (CV) values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean, the highest being for Seq_3_D6. Standard deviation (STD) values residuals vary significantly across sequences, with Seq_5_D7 having a wide range of prediction errors and Seq_7_D3 having a narrower range, suggesting more accurate predictions. The MAE values showcase Seq_5_D2 as the worst and Seq_7_D5 as the best, in terms of performance. R^2 values are generally high, indicating that the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data. Most sequences have R^2 values above 0.95, suggesting good model fit.

As for residuals by depth, the model's mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. Depth 2 (D2) has the highest mean residual, indicating a slight bias. High CV values indicate significant variability in residuals, with D6 having a slightly higher CV. STD values are consistently low, the highest being 0.0.213913 for D2 followed closely by D1. R^2 values are generally very high, indicating that the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data. In summary, the model performs well overall, but there are depths with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly D1 and D2.

The Random Forest model showed good accuracy in predicting sequences with mean residuals close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. However, some sequences, like Seq_5_D2 and Seq_5_D3, showed higher mean residuals, suggesting slight overestimation. The CV values are high, indicating significant

variability in the residuals relative to the mean, particularly for Seq_5_D6 with extremely large values. STD values are quite varied, with Seq_5_D2 having a wide range of prediction errors and Seq_7_D7 having a narrower range, suggesting more accurate predictions. The MAE values are quite balanced, and R^2 values are generally high, the lowest being Seq_2_D6 with an R^2 of 0.918942.

The model's mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. D1 has the highest mean residual at 0.004844, indicating slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. The STD range of residuals varies significantly across depths, with Depth 1 having a wide range of prediction errors and Depth 5 having a narrower range. D1 has an RMSE of 0.250305, indicating substantial prediction errors. R^2 values are generally high, indicating that the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data. In summary, the model performs well overall, but there are depths with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Depth 1.

The ENR model showed residuals with mean close to zero, but larger standard deviations compared to other models. The mean residuals for most sequences are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. However, some sequences, such as Seq_8_D1, show higher mean residuals, suggesting slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. STD values indicate Seq_8_D2 has having a wide range of prediction errors and Seq_7_D5 having a narrower range, suggesting more accurate predictions. MAE are slightly higher than for other models all across the board, indication an higher average magnitude of the residuals. The RMSE values are the highest when comparing to the other categorical models, by a significant margin, reflecting the inclusion of large errors in the model. R^2 values are generally high, indicating that the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data. Most sequences have R^2 values above 0.98, suggesting good model fit. However, Seq_2_D7 has a lower R^2 value, indicating less variance for this sequence.

As for the analysis by depth, the mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. D1 has the highest mean residual at 0.006428, indicating slight bias. High CV values indicate significant variability in residuals relative to the mean.

STD values provide insight into the spread of residuals, with higher values indicating greater variability and lower values suggesting more consistent ones. The range of residuals varies significantly across depths, with Depth 2 having a wide range of prediction errors and Depth 7 having a narrower range, suggesting more accurate predictions. D1 has an RMSE of 0.351105, indicating substantial prediction errors. R^2 values are generally high, indicating that the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data. Most depths have R^2 values above 0.98, suggesting good model fit. The model's performance is generally accurate, but there are areas with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Depth 1.

3.2 Models used for numerical data

For the numerical data the models used are RF, ANN, SVR and XGB. All model results are subject to 30 iterations and 3-fold cross-validation to optimize hyperparameters, except the SVR which due to time and computational requirements is only subject to a 10 iterations 3-fold cross-validation.

3.2.1 Numerical Model Performance

In accordance with the section above, now we present a detailed overview of the performance of the main numerical models used.

The Random Forest model demonstrated excellent performance, excelling in various evaluation metrics. The MSE is 0.0084, while the RMSE is 0.0543. The MAE is 0.0086, indicating high prediction accuracy. The R^2 is 0.9948, showing that the model explains almost all the data variability. Additionally, the explained variance score is 0.9949, reinforcing the model's high capacity to capture data variability.

The SVR model also demonstrated notable performance, with very low error metrics and high accuracy. The MSE is 0.0003, the RMSE is 0.0162, and the MAE is 0.0098. The R^2 is 0.9945, indicating that the model is highly effective in explaining data variability. The EVS is 0.9947, confirming the excellent predictive capacity of the SVR model.

The ANN model demonstrated inferior performance compared to the other models but still provided useful results. The MSE is 0.0885, the RMSE is 0.2224, and the MAE is 0.1103. The R^2 is 0.6379, showing that the model explains a significant part, but not the majority, of the data variability. The EVS is 0.6393, indicating that the neural network may be useful in specific scenarios where data complexity is high.

The XGB model also demonstrated excellent performance, with low error metrics and high accuracy. The MSE is 0.0084, the RMSE is 0.0567, and the MAE is 0.0119. The R^2 is 0.9927, showing that the model is highly effective in explaining data variability. The EVS is 0.9928, reinforcing the robustness of the XGB model for accurate predictions.

3.2.2 Residuals of Numerical Data

The residuals for numerical data can be found in ANNEX I – Residuals of numerical algorithms used. These pertain to all the algorithms used to work with numerical data.

The Random Forest model showed good prediction accuracy for most target variables, with mean residuals close to zero. However, some sequences, like Seq_5_D1 and Seq_5_D6, showed higher mean residuals, indicating slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. STD values showcase Seq_5_D7 as having the widest range of prediction errors and Seq_7_D5 having a narrower range, suggesting more accurate predictions. The MAE values are all under 0.07 indicating a good model performance. Seq_5_D7 had an RMSE of 0.223209, indicating substantial prediction errors for this predictor. R^2 values are generally extremely high, the lowest being 0.993819. In conclusion, the Random Forest model performed exceptionally well overall, but there are sequences with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Seq_5.

As for the depth analysis, the mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. D1 has the highest mean residual at -0.001285, indicating slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals. STD values point to D1 has having a wider range of prediction errors and Depth 5 has having a narrower range. D1 has the highest RMSE of 0.061865, which indicates the errors in

the predictions are not substantial. R^2 values are extremely high, above 0.997 indicating that the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data. In summary, the model performs exceptionally well overall, but there are depths with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Depth 1.

The SVR model, which predicts the mean of a sequence, has residuals close to zero, indicating good accuracy. However, some sequences, like Seq_7_D5 and Seq_7_D6, show slightly higher mean residuals, suggesting slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. STD values indicate Seq_2_D1 having a wide range of prediction errors and Seq_7_D5 having a narrower range. The MAE values are higher for Seq_2_D1 and are balanced in the other target variables. Seq_2_D1 has the highest RMSE of 0.034696, indicating substantial prediction errors. Most sequences have R^2 values above 0.99, suggesting excellent model fit. In conclusion, the SVR model performs exceptionally well overall, but there are some target predictors with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Seq_2_D1.0

Regarding the residual analysis by depth, the mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. Depth 7 has the highest mean residual, indicating slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in residuals. STD values point to Depth 1 having the wider range of prediction errors and D5 having a narrower range. Depth 1 has an RMSE of 0.017491, indicating moderate prediction errors. Most depths have R^2 values above 0.99, suggesting excellent model fit. In summary, the model performs exceptionally well overall, but there are depths with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Depth 1.

The XGB model showed good accuracy with residuals close to zero and low standard deviations, indicating good predictions. However, some sequences, such as Seq_5_D1 and Seq_5_D3, showed higher mean residuals, suggesting slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. The STD values highlight Seq_5_D1 having a wide range of prediction errors and Seq_7_D3 having the narrower range. Seq_5_D1 had an RMSE of 0.350414 indicating substantial prediction errors. R^2 values are generally high, indicating that

the model explains a large proportion of the variance in the data, the lowest being Seq_2_D7. In conclusion, the XGB model performed exceptionally well overall, but there are sequences with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Seq_5_D1.

Regarding the analysis of residuals by depth, the mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. STD values showcase Depth 1 as having a wider range of prediction errors and Depth 5 having a narrower range. Most depths have R^2 values above 0.99, suggesting excellent model fit. However, Depth 7 has a slightly lower R^2 value, indicating less variance for this depth. In conclusion, the model performs exceptionally well overall, but there are depths with higher variability and larger prediction errors, particularly in Depth 1.

The ANN model's mean residuals are generally unbiased, but some sequences, like Seq_8_D6, show higher mean residuals, indicating slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in the residuals relative to the mean. Standard deviation (STD) values highlight Seq_8_D2 as having a wider range of prediction errors and Seq_6_D7 having a narrower range, suggesting more accurate predictions. Most predictions of the target variables have R^2 values above 0.90, suggesting good model fit. However, there is quite a differentiation between targets in this model with Seq_4_D4 scoring R^2 value of 0.063991, indicating a very poor fit.

Regarding the residual analysis by depth, the mean residuals are close to zero, indicating unbiased predictions. Depth 2 has the highest mean residual, indicating slight bias. The CV values are high, indicating significant variability in residuals relative to the mean. STD values point to Depth 1 having a wider range of prediction errors and Depth 7 having a narrower range. R^2 vary substantially, from D5 scoring 0.547475 to D1 scoring 0.958314. This also showcases the ANN is actually better at predicting variables on the top 2 layers than on deeper layers, going against the patterns of performance across all the studied models.

3.3 Most important predictors

The most important predictors are studied with two distinct organizations in mind, depth and dataset. This is the adopted strategy since the database at hand is quite complex. Being that organic carbon is selected as the target variable, it must be highlighted that this is a misnomer, when in fact for each parish there are up to 12 sequences and always 7 layers of depth. So potentially, each parish would have 84 target variables.

The outputs for this section are produced by the machine learning algorithms described above, selecting only the 50 most important by model.

3.3.1 Results by depth

The soil is built up of various geological phenomena, and its naturally stratified into layers depending on location, geological factors and climatic factors. This produces a variety of soils at different depths. To factor these into the models, we listed the most important predictors of each depth, from 1 up to 7. Additionally, please refer to Table I for depth measure standards.

In the sections below, features will be presented in a feature target composite name, which is a direct result of concatenation between the feature and the target variable (ORG_CARBON) it affects. For increased readability, the feature names referenced below will be shortened (ie, Seq_7_D1_TOTAL_N_Seq_7_D1_ORG_CARBON will be Seq_7_D1_TOTAL_N) or adequately paraphrased. Since there can be up to 12 sequences (or soil types) per depth layer, and therefore up to 12 organic carbon target variables per depth layer, we focus on the depth which includes all D1 organic carbon variables and disregard the soil sequence for this analysis. The features are categorized based on their source dataset: HWSD2, CHELSA, COS2007, and INE. The importance score indicates how much each feature contributes to the model's prediction.

Depth 1

Starting with the soil variables from dataset HWSD2, we see that total soil nitrogen content has the highest importance score of approximately 0.985013, making it the

most crucial feature for predicting organic carbon at soil depth 1. In fact, three out of the top seven variables relate to total soil nitrogen content, making it a very relevant predictor for organic carbon at the first depth.

Similarly, features like Seq_8_D1_HWSD2_LAYERS_DRAINAGE which can be read as the drainage type has high importance (0.980381) for organic carbon values on the top layer. The drainage is presented five times by 2 different models (XGB_CAT and RF_CAT) in the top 10 variables.

Moving on to the CHELSA variables, Media_PR_2001 and Media_TAS_1991, mean annual precipitation and mean annual temperature have lower importance scores of 0.000950 and 0.000896, respectively. These features represent precipitation and temperature data from CHELSA and, while not as crucial as the soil variables, they still contribute to the model's predictions showcasing the influence of earlier temperatures and precipitation on soil organic carbon.

For the COS2007 Map variables, the highest is Area_ha_2.3.3.1_Agriculture with natural and seminatural spaces, has an importance score of 0.000708. Other notable features are the percentage of discontinuous built surface with 0.000460, and the percentage of olive groves scoring 0.000436. This dataset points to a mixed importance of percentage and area between vegetation (farmed and natural) and build surface land.

Lastly, the INE predictors, have low importance score for this depth, being the Agri surface (ha) by location (NUTS-2013), VS (very small) < 8 000 €, Animal Products; 2009, the highest with a score of 0.000758. This is followed by Agri surface (ha) by location (NUTS-2013), VS (very small) < 8 000 €, Arable crops; 2009 with 0.000607 and altitude scoring 0.000592

In summary for this depth, the most important features belong to the HWSD2 dataset, while other sources fall to importances with magnitudes one thousand times lower.

Depth 2

For depth two, the most important predictor for SOC is again the soil total nitrogen content scoring approximately 0.985830.

Also the drainage type dominates at this depth, with both XGB_CAT and RF_CAT models pointing to high importance values of approximately 0.976565. A new

addition is the soil texture, coming up as the third most important predictor with a score of approximately 0.866895. Finally, the soil bulk density is also highlighted with a value of approximately 0.776135.

The CHELSA variables, such as StdDev_PR_2001 and StdDev_PR_1994, have lower importance scores of 0.000304 and 0.000284, respectively. These features represent precipitation data from CHELSA and, while not as crucial as the soil variables, they still contribute to the model's predictions.

The INE variables, such as Agri surface (ha) by location (NUTS-2013), VS (very small) < 8 000 €, Unclassified Farms;1999, have varying importance scores. The highest among them is 0.203175618, indicating a moderate level of importance in the NN model. The curious insight here is that the importance is that Unclassified farms, and poly livestock farms, particularly small and very small, have the highest impact, being followed again by poly livestock medium farms. This data seems to point to a relation between the livestock activities and soil organic carbon.

Finally, the Land Use and Occupation Map variable listed pertains the area of natural watercourses, with an importance value of 0.000091, which is over ten thousand times lower importance than the top variables, but its presence indicates there is influence of watercourses on SOC.

Depth 3

Starting with the soil variables, drainage is at the top scoring 0.974454 followed by soil total nitrogen content, with an importance score of 0.899211.

A few new additions start appearing, the first being clay (expressed as a percentage) with a score of 0.778474. Another new addition to the top predictors at this depth is gypsum; a salt found in driest areas, can be found in various forms, including desert rose, fibre, crystals, or soft forms, scoring approximately 0.886796. The base saturation as a measure cation exchange capacity (BSAT); which measures exchangeable cations (nutrients) in soil; also appears by the first time with high importance, scoring 0.742031. Another entry of relevance is the WRB_PHASES predictor which indicates that the type of topsoil influences SOC at depth 3.

The CHELSA predictors of most relevance are the mean annual temperature in 1998 (0.000183) followed by coefficient of variation of the mean annual temperature in

2001 (0.000104). These are somewhat mixed and do not exhibit any particular tendency, however their magnitude is very low when compared with soil predictors from HWSDv2.0.

The COS2007 predictors with the most importance at this depth are first of all hardwood forests scoring 0.000967. Others listed include commerce, complex plots/cultural mosaics, spontaneous pastures and olive groves, ranging from 0.000220 to 0.000146.

The INE variables, such as burnt area (%) in 1977, has an importance score of 0.152458. This appearance of this predictor at depth 3, indicates a possible influence of the consequence of wildfires and the 40-60 cm depth layer of soil organic carbon in a period of approximately 20 years. Also, the practice of polyculture within medium sized farms ($25000 < 100000 \text{€}$) scores high at this depth (0.006370).

Depth 4

At Depth 4, the analysis shows a most interesting influence of topsoil drainage type on the SOC with a score of 0.982018. The carbon-nitrogen ratio is also very influential with a score of 0.855398, with the additional insight that the C/N ratio here referred is from depth 2, 20-40 cm. This is followed by soil total nitrogen content with 0.817917 of depth 3 and gypsum of depth 5 with 0.761320. This depth showcases the influence across depths of several predictors of soil organic carbon.

The CHELSA predictors with most relevance are the standard deviation of mean precipitation in 2002 scoring 0.132843, followed by mean annual temperature of 2000 scoring 0.126217. After these are two predictors relating to the coefficient of variation of precipitation, in 1992 and 2004, scoring 0.119735 and 0.115827.

The COS2007 predictors, such as the area (hectares) of leisure, cultural and touristic installations take the top with 0.266782, 0.185641 and 0.178636. One important addition at this level is the influence of oceanic area at 0.152957 and areas classified as trash and scrap, scoring 0.116488.

The INE predictor, such as area of fires in hectares for the years 1977 and 1980 are the top two predictor here with scores of 0.749828 and 0.591106, respectively. These are followed by a burnt area (percentage) with 0.552411. Again, this showcases the influence of burned zones and SOC at a significant depth. The next predictors of

interest are relating to agricultural surface area by use, being the highest polyculture in medium farms, followed by permanent crops in very small farms, for the year 1999, scoring 0.0430772 and 0.275315 respectively.

Depth 5

In this depth the most relevant predictor of the HWSD2 dataset is drainage of the topsoil layer scoring 0.982133, followed by the C/N ratio of depth 4, with a score of 0.777315. One unexpected predictor is the drainage type of the 7th layer, with a score of 0.674216, followed by the soil total nitrogen content and the clay of depth 2 with 0.658523 and 0.578915. These predictors reflect the high importance of drainage and appropriate soil texture and structure.

The CHELSA predictors of relevance are the mean precipitation in 1994 and the standard deviation of the mean precipitation for 2003, with scores of 0.000443 and 0.000165, respectively.

The COS2007 predictors of relevance are area of quarries with 0.157284, followed by modified/artificial watercourse scoring 0.140328.

The INE predictors are headed by the number of fires in 1979, 0.123327, followed by for Poly livestock practices for medium farms in 1999, scoring 0.002044, and, in the same year and practice for small farms, with a score of 0.000183.

Depth 6

At this depth, the most relevant predictor is the topsoil drainage type with a score of 0.972376, followed by the soil texture of the 7th depth (0.948081). These are followed by soil total nitrogen content (0.780911) and coarse percentage of the 5th layer (0.775697) again showcasing the influence of soil structure in SOC values.

The CHELSA predictors for this depth are firstly the mean precipitation in 1996 (0.000247) followed by the standard deviation of mean annual temperature in 1991(0.000161); very closely tied with the mean precipitation in 1994 in terms of importance (0.000159).

The COS2007 predictors of interest in this depth pertain mostly to forest and vegetation areas, such as sparse vegetation (0.004854), wild pine forests

(0.000290), percentage of eucalyptus forest (0.000120). This is followed by sparsely built surface (0.000116) and woodlands (0.000095).

The INE predictors of relevance start off with agricultural surface area of large farms dedicated to poly livestock production in 1999 (0.089748), followed by the area of medium sized farms of vegetable production in the same year (0.079130)

Depth 7

Finally, Depth 7 starts off with the drainage type of the topsoil layer (0.974854), followed by the coarse percentage of the previous depth (0.773525). This depth showcases a few new additions of predictors, for example the effective cation exchange rate of the topsoil layer (0.545351) and the aluminum saturation (0.497041). Other prevalent predictors are the CN ratio of the 3rd depth (0.537555), bulk density (0.507095) and soil total nitrogen content (0.453538).

The CHELSA predictors of interest are the coefficient of variation for precipitation in 2003 (0.001161), the coefficient of variation for temperature for 2002 (0.000695).

For the COS2007 predictors the most relevant is discontinuous built surface area (0.003079), followed by area of temporary rainfed and irrigated crops and orchards scoring 0.000451 and 0.000417 respectively.

Finally, the most relevant predictor for the INE dataset is the number of fires in 1995 (0.000087).

3.3.2 Results by dataset

The article identified key predictors of soil properties across different depths and datasets. This analysis is, as mentioned before, done by selecting the 50 most important predictors by model. The total lump sum of predictors at the start of this phase is 1100. The first metric we can assert from this is that since 700 are from the HWSD2 database and 400 are from the other databases, it would mean that the soil predictors have been regarded by the various models to be more important overall for defining SOC.

For each dataset used, the predictor frequency is traced, regarding the model that originated it. The percentages presented below refer to the 50 most important predictors for each model. Therefore, there are cases where not all datasets are included.

Table II - Frequency of predictors by dataset and ML model. Top 50 predictors per model.

Dataset	Model	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	Total
HWSD2	EN	0.17	0.19	0.13	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.69
HWSD2	NN	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.25
HWSD2	RF	0.06	0.11	0.09	0.05	0.13	0.14	0.12	0.71
HWSD2	RF_CAT	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.04	0.13	0.09	0.11	0.71
HWSD2	SVR	0.15	0.17	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.70
HWSD2	XGB	0.10	0.15	0.11	0.04	0.10	0.09	0.12	0.71
HWSD2	XGB_CAT	0.06	0.10	0.12	0.07	0.10	0.13	0.12	0.70
CHELSEA	NN	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06
CHELSEA	RF	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.17	0.36
CHELSEA	XGB	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.09
COS2007	NN	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.11
COS2007	RF	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.10
COS2007	XGB	0.10	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.17
INE	NN	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.15	0.09	0.04	0.00	0.33
INE	RF	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.22
INE	SVR	0.00	0.03	0.19	0.07	0.12	0.20	0.11	0.71
INE	XGB	0.17	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.39

Table II shows that for the HWSD2 dataset, the predictor are similarly weighted between models, except for the Neural Network model, which results indicate a lower importance for predictors belonging to this dataset.

The predictors from the CHELSA dataset mostly originated from the RF model, with trace importance for predictors from the NN and XGB models.

The COS2007 dataset predictors are more important for the XGB model, followed by the NN and RF models.

The INE dataset predictors are of high importance for the SVR model, moderate importance for the XGB and low importance for the NN and RF models.

To summarize, this data highlights the predictor importance of predictors from the HWSD2 database in the prediction of SOC, followed by the predictors from the INE database. The predictors from COS2007 and CHELSA are somewhat tied for the third place.

3.3.4 Overall predictors results by dataset

The predictors from the HWSD2 dataset consistently emerged as the most influential across all models analysed. The top predictor overall is soil total nitrogen content, with the highest importance scores of 0.985830 and 0.985013. Total nitrogen is crucial for plant growth, and its availability can significantly impact soil productivity. Following closely is the drainage of the topsoil, which is a key predictor across six of the seven depths, with importance values ranging from 0.982133 to 0.972376. This highlights the critical role of topsoil drainage capacity in influencing soil organic carbon (SOC) levels. Other significant predictors include soil texture (score of 0.948081), gypsum with a score of 0.886796, carbon-nitrogen ratio (0.855398), and various soil phases and properties such as clay content (0.778474) and bulk density (0.776135). The base saturation (0.742031) also plays a significant role. These features indicate that soil total nitrogen content and topsoil drainage are critical for predicting organic carbon content. The high importance scores suggest that soil properties are the primary drivers of organic carbon levels, emphasizing the need for effective soil management practices to enhance SOC

The CHELSA variables included in the models have very low importance scores, indicating they are less influential. Standard deviation of precipitation in 2002 (0.132843) referencing the organic carbon content in soil at depth 4.

The mean temperature in 2000 also has a relevant importance of 0.126217. Curiously enough this predictor is also relating depth 4. In fact, the 17 highest scoring predictors for CHELSA database pertain to depth four, which suggests that the influence of temperature and precipitation may be dependent on the depth of the SOC in the soil strata.

These low importance scores suggest that climate variables from CHELSA have a minimal impact on predicting soil organic carbon content in these models.

The COS2007 predictors, overall, have low importance scores.

The highest scoring predictors at this depth relate to leisure installations (0.266782) and cultural installations with a score of 0.185641.

The top results are populated by predictors influence depths 4 and 5 and mostly urban installations, quarries scrapyards, beaches and dunes, which may suggest a relation between these human constructions and SOC at these depths.

These moderate to low importance scores indicate that land use variables have a minimal impact on predicting soil organic carbon content in these models.

The INE variables have the moderately high importance scores, indicating they are somewhat influential in the models. Top results are mostly populated with predictors influencing depths 4 and 5.

The highest scoring predictor is burnt area (ha) in 1977, followed by burnt area (ha) in 1980 with scores of 0.749828 and 0.591106, respectively. The third is burnt area (%) for 1977 scoring 0.552411.

The fact that the data is headed by 3 datapoints from the burnt land (all at a depth of 60-80 cm) almost 2 decades beforehand, showcases the distal temporal importance of these factors in SOC, and the depths which can impact.

Other relevant predictors are the agricultural surface area in 1999 for medium polyculture farms (0.430772) and for very small permanent culture farms (0.275315). Both predictors relate to the 4th depth SOC, reinforcing a possible tendency.

3.4 Per parish data

This section aimed to analyse soil properties and organic carbon content across different municipalities and parishes. Data from multiple Excel sheets is merged to create a comprehensive dataset, including numeric and categorical soil properties. A weighted average is calculated for each property, considering the proportion of each soil mapping unit (SMU) within a parish. The most common categories and frequencies are determined to summarize dominant soil characteristics within each parish. The data is aggregated at the municipality level to provide a broader overview of soil properties across larger administrative regions.

A clustering analysis is performed to identify patterns and group similar regions. The process involved data preparation, the elbow method, K-means clustering, and cluster analysis. 30 clusters are defined, and the top and bottom 10 clusters are selected for detailed analysis, focusing on organic carbon content.

3.4.1 Per parish K-means Cluster results

The analysis identified the top and bottom five clusters based on overall soil organic carbon (SOC) content. For each cluster, the top 20 features by variance are examined. The cluster with the highest SOC overall is Cluster 26, with an average score of 6.257654. This cluster is followed by Clusters 19 (3.719091), 21 (3.646899), 25 (3.639344), and 0 (3.631015). The clusters with the lowest SOC averages are Cluster 28 (0.495917), Cluster 11 (0.551189), Cluster 24 (0.576543), Cluster 29 (0.590360), and Cluster 12 (0.590360).

Subsequently, the five clusters with the highest SOC (top group) and the five clusters with the lowest SOC (bottom group) are studied to identify similar and distinctive intra- and inter-cluster features. This approach resulted in the identification of the ten most distinctive features, from which we highlight three main features: first is the impermeable layer depth, which appears as distinctive in 35% of the clusters; followed by drainage, which appears in 29%, and then the type of soil (WRB_PHASE), which appears in 24%. Finally, soil texture and bulk reference are also relevant for distinction in 8% and 3% of the clusters, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

The first step in this article is the selection of relevant databases to understand the influences on soil properties related to organic carbon content. The Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD v2.0), developed by FAO and IIASA, is used, consolidating information from various sources, including the European Soil Database and national soil maps. This database provides detailed soil attributes across seven depth layers, such as texture, bulk density, organic carbon content, pH, and cation exchange capacity.

The second database is the Land Use and Occupation Map (COS2007v3.0) from the Directorate-General for Territory, offering detailed information on land use and occupation in mainland Portugal by parish.

The third database is CHELSA, providing high-resolution climate data, including bioclimatic indices for precipitation and mean annual temperature.

The fourth database is obtained from the National Institute of Statistics (INE), containing information on agricultural enterprise managers, economic dimensions, technical-economic orientation, agricultural machinery, irrigated land, burned areas, and population density.

The datasets are then merged into what is the first output, herein named Combined Database (see Figure 1). This database joins the four independent datasets and lists them by Portuguese parish. For this, some of the data had to be georeferenced, mainly the HWSD v2.0 data, to allow for compatibility within the database. The georeferencing of HWSD v2.0 data is performed using QGIS, adding information about Portuguese districts, municipalities, and parishes.

The missing values are handled by normalising the weights of each valid value, ensuring accurate representation of the remaining data points. An overall flowchart regarding the activities of this article can be seen on Figure 1.

After data processing, leading up to the combined database, other tasks are needed to further refine the structure of the combined database. These operations are comprised mainly of joining, organizing, classifying, binning, cleaning and rechecking.

The resulting final database is what is the first output of this project and serves as the working basis for the following machine learning algorithms.

The creation, training, and testing of various machine learning models began, using Python and the Spyder IDE. The algorithms used included Random Forest, XGB, ANNs, SVR, and ENR. The data are divided into two parts: categorical data and numerical data, creating two datasets for each parish. These datasets are used to train and test the models. The performance of the models is evaluated, the

Figure 1 - Flowchart of activities developed during the article.

residuals and the most important features (predictors) are identified for each model. These results can be observed in section 3. Results of this working paper.

In order to account for **data validation**, a K-fold cross-validation method is used to randomly split the data into k subsets for training and testing, reducing bias. Ten rounds of cross-validations are performed, training the model on all but one subset and testing on the excluded subset. Performance metrics included Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), R-squared (R^2), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Explained Variance Score (EVS), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

In addition to machine learning models, **clustering** of parishes is performed to identify patterns and groupings based on soil characteristics and other variables. The K-means algorithm is used to cluster the parishes, allowing for a more detailed analysis of similarities and differences between regions. This approach helped identify areas with similar characteristics.

The **clustering analysis** identified various clusters above 3% SOC, which is considered above average, and one above 5% which is considered the best. The worst performing clusters presented SOC values below 0.6% which is considered very poor. The article of the most distinctive features between the best and worst SOC groups revealed that the depth of the impermeable layer, drainage, and soil type are the primary features that differentiate the clusters with the highest and lowest SOC levels. Soil texture and bulk reference play a smaller but still relevant role.

Regarding **the model performance results**, for the models used to process numerical data, the RF and XGB models consistently outperformed the Neural Network model, demonstrating high accuracy and robustness. The SVR model also showed excellent predictive capacity, making it a reliable choice for such tasks. The ANN model, while capable of capturing complex patterns, requires further fine-tuning and larger datasets to achieve comparable accuracy. As for categorical model performance, the RF and XGB models consistently outperformed the ENR model in predicting categorical variables. Both RF and XGB demonstrated high accuracy and

robustness, making them reliable choices for such tasks. The ENR model, on the other hand, showed limited effectiveness and may require further optimization or larger datasets to improve its predictive capabilities. In summary, the choice of the ideal model may depend on the specific characteristics of the data and the application context.

The **use of machine learning algorithms** as a tool for analysis of soil organic carbon predictors, within the final database across different depths, reveals significant variations in the importance and influence of various factors. At Depth 1, total soil nitrogen content emerges as the most crucial predictor, with drainage type also playing a significant role. As we move to Depth 2, soil texture and bulk density become more prominent, alongside the continued importance of total nitrogen content and drainage. Depth 3 introduces new predictors such as clay content and gypsum, indicating the influence of soil composition on SOC. By Depth 4, the carbon-nitrogen ratio from previous depths and the presence of gypsum from deeper layers highlight the cross-depth interactions affecting SOC. Depth 5 sees the continued dominance of drainage type, with the addition of predictors like soil texture and structure from various depths. At Depth 6, the influence of soil texture and coarse percentage becomes more pronounced, while Depth 7 introduces new predictors such as effective cation exchange rate and aluminium saturation, showcasing the complex interplay of soil properties at greater depths.

Regarding **the residuals analysis**, the categorical models which performed best are the XGB and RF models, which stood out with smaller residuals and high accuracy, while the ENR model exhibited larger residuals and lower accuracy. The residuals of numerical models point that the RF, SVR and XGB models show very high R^2 , indicating good fits. However, these models encounter larger prediction errors in some sequences, particularly on SOC of the top layers. On the other hand, the ANN model showed a moderately good fit with most R^2 values above 0.90, but it exhibits significant variability in predictions, and very poor fit in deeper layers.

These findings on organic carbon in mainland Portugal presented here are not without **limitations**, including reliance on existing databases, a specific geographic

region, and potential data gaps. Factors influencing the current analysis include variability in predictor importance, limited temporal data, geographical and climatic specificity, and complex interactions between predictors. Variability in importance scores across different depths makes it difficult to draw definitive conclusions about influential factors for SOC.

<i>Depth</i>	<i>HWSD2 (Top Predictors & Scores)</i>	<i>CHELSA (Top Predictor & Score)</i>	<i>COS2007 (Top Predictor & Score)</i>	<i>INE (Top Predictor & Score)</i>	<i>HWSD2 vs INE</i>	<i>HWSD2 vs CHELSA</i>	<i>HWSD2 vs COS2007</i>
1	Total N (0.985013), Drainage (0.980381)	MAP (0.000950)	Agri + Seminatural (0.000708)	Agri surface (0.000758)	1293x	1032x	1384x
2	Total N (0.985830), Drainage (0.976565)	StdDev_PR_2001 (0.000304)	—	Agri surface (0.203176)	4.85x	3241x	3471x
3	Drainage (0.974454), Total N (0.89211)	MAT 1998 (0.000183)	Hardwood forests (0.000967)	Burnt area % (0.152458)	6.39x	5324x	1008x
4	Drainage (0.982018), C _r /N ratio (0.855398)	StdDev PR 2002 (0.132843)	Leisure/Tourism (0.266782)	Fire area 1977 (0.749828)	1.31x	7.39x	3.68x
5	Drainage (0.982133), C _r /N (0.77315)	PR 1994 (0.000443)	Quarries (0.157284)	Fires 1979 (0.123327)	7.96x	2217x	6.24x
6	Drainage (0.972376), Texture (0.948081)	PR 1996 (0.000247)	Sparse veg. (0.004854)	Large farms poly livestock (0.089748)	10.84x	3937x	200x
7	Drainage (0.974854), Coarse % (0.773525)	CV PR 2003 (0.001161)	Built surface (0.003079)	Fires 1995 (0.000087)	11203x	840x	317x

In Table III the comparison of the highest normalized predictors (importance) for all databases is presented. Here it is possible to observe that in all depths, the predictors belonging to the HWSD2 dataset are the most relevant, the closest match being the predictor from INE in depth 4. However, if we compare the 4 highest predictors for this depth instead of just the highest, the factor is increased up to 1,5 (12% increase) approximately, reinforcing the importance of HWSD2 predictors

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work successfully integrates multiple datasets—including the Harmonized World Soil Database, COS2007v3.0 land use data, CHELSA climate data, and socioeconomic data from the National Institute of Statistics—to analyse soil organic carbon content across mainland Portugal. By combining these diverse sources, the research provides a comprehensive framework for understanding SOC dynamics and their relationship with soil, climate, and land use factors.

Future recommendations for improving the accuracy and reliability of Soil Organic Carbon prediction models include expanding temporal coverage, enhancing geographic representation, addressing data gaps, investigating predictor interactions, developing integrated models, using advanced modelling techniques like machine learning and deep learning, and promoting collaborative research between researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders. The dataset could be extended to incorporate additional variables influencing soil properties. Further exploration of advanced machine learning techniques could provide more accurate insights into soil dynamics, particularly after a successful clustering technique is applied.

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ANNEX I – RESIDUALS OF NUMERICAL ALGORITHMS USED

ANNEX II – RESIDUAL PLOTS FOR CATEGORICAL ALGORITHMS USED

